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Extracted Lignin from Native Australian Lignocellulosic biomass as a Powerful Agent for High-Performance Composites

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Objectives

- Modification and optimizing the lignin extraction process from Australian bio source with ionic liquid treatment.
- Characterising the properties of extracted Ionic liquid Lignin from native Australian sources.
- Comprehensive characterisation study of the manufactured IL-Lignin based epoxy composites to study the effect of IL-Lignin solution on the thermal, mechanical and morphological properties of the composites.

Current Study for the Lignin Based Bio Composites

Focus on Lignin in Research Field

Figure 1: Number of publications through the year with keyword 'lignin' in the titles. (Scopus web search)

Why Ionic liquid As Separation Aid

Green

Low melting points

High thermal stability

Negligible vapour pressure

Non volatility

Inflammability

- **Ammonium Based Ionic liquid**
- Triethylammonium hydrogen sulfate (TEAS) $[(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}][\text{HSO}_4]$
- Efficiently pre-treat lignocellulose biomass
- Have lower environmental impact due to a reduction in waste by-products, solvent losses, energy usage and CO_2 generation
- Synthesized through simple neutralization of

an organic amine with a mineral acid

- To yield an IL that does not require purification
- Bulk production of this IL will be as low as $\$1.24\text{kg}^{-1}$

Experimental

Extraction of Lignin

Thermal Degradation Study

- First wt. Loss between 200 - 300°C
- Second wt. loss between 400 - 550°C
- For Neat epoxy T_{max} is 372°C,
- 2% wt. ILL-epoxy composite is 408°C

Chemical Characterisation

Table 1: Functional groups corresponding to the wavenumbers from FTIR analysis

Responsible groups	Acacia Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Eucalyptus Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Pine Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Reference Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)
Esterification of phenolic group	1710	1711	1720	1710-1736
Phenolic OH group	1485	1492	1500	1450- 1500
Syringyl	1200	1200	1200	1150-1200
guaiacyl	1300	1300	1300	1250-1300

Chemical Characterisation

δ ppm	Assignment
0.85	Alkyl (methyl)
1.18	Alkyl (Methylene)
1.67	Alkyl (Methine)
1.98	Allylic (C is next to a pi bond)
2.29	Aromatic acetate
2.51	Protons in DMSO
3.10	Methoxy group
3.38	Protons in water in DMSO
6.72	H α in β -O-4 structures
6.86	Aromatic protons in syringyl units (S)
6.98	Aromatic protons on benzaldehyde units
7.30	Aromatic protons in guaiacyl units (G)
8.88	Formyl protons in benzaldehyde units

Surface Properties Analysis

3D printed IL-Lignin solution by Aerosol jet printing process

(a) Optical image

(b)

(c) Height

Amplitude

AFM images (10 x 10 μm area) of ILL (C)

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) Analysis

Curing behaviour of the Composite Systems

Table 2. Thermal properties of IL-Lignin-epoxy based composites

Sample Epoxy - % wt. ILL	Peak Temperature T_P (°C)	Activation energy E_{Act} (kJ/mol)	Heat of reaction ΔH (J/g)
Neat epoxy	146.81	122.6	1021.79
1 % ILL	149.22	118.6	991.3
1.5 % ILL	147.10	81.84	957.4
2 % ILL	144.20	50.7	627.1

Mechanical Properties Study

Conclusions

- The curing kinetics studies reveal that IL-Lignin epoxy composites show a faster conversion at the start of the curing process, and overall higher degrees of cure compared to the neat epoxy system.
- FTIR analysis evidences the weakening of anhydride hardener while reacting with IL-Lignin and eases the path of cross-linking for the epoxy resin.
- XPS analysis also shows a clear peak for ester group which appeared from the bond cleavage of anhydride hardener.
- Moreover, NMR data displays the presence of guaiacyl units (G) and p-hydroxyphenyl units (H) of the lignin structure.
- Thermal degradation experiments show that a small inclusion of IL-Lignin into the epoxy matrix can remarkably improve the thermal stabilities by a 40% increase in the decomposition temperature.
- However, there is a decrease of 50 °C in glass transition temperature for IL-Lignin epoxy composite.
- Additionally, AFM and DLS studies confirm particle size distribution, average size length (273.80 nm) of lignin particles in IL and average surface roughness of epoxy composites.
- In terms of mechanical properties, as a result of functionalisation induced by addition of IL-Lignin, the flexural strength and flexural modulus of the 2 wt% IL-Lignin epoxy composites are increased by 80% and 57%, respectively, compared to the neat epoxy matrix

Thank you